

GENDER EXPRESSION OF ZOONYMS IN UZBEK, RUSSIA AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES: LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL ANALYSIS

Mamatxonova Gulmirabonu Kamoliddiq qizi
Mirzayeva Dilshoda Ikromjonovna

Farg'ona davlat universiteti

Imgliz filologiyasi kafedrasini mudiri
filologiya fanlari falsafa doktori, dotsent
gmamatkhonova@bk.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13922899>

ANNOTATION: This thesis is about culture, like language, is a complementary part. Language is a component of culture, it is the most important component in its formation and storage. Language units, and especially units of the lexical-phraseological language level, are a "mirror of folk culture", semantic and structural dictionary connections reflect the actual and important connections for a person between objects and subjects of the surrounding reality, its ideal and real subjects and, thus, convey the features of the national culture.

Key words: Phraseologism, artistic image, linguistic units, stylistic device, image.

Phraseology permeates our entire daily life, helps to express our thoughts more precisely, and manifests itself not only in language, but also in speech, thinking and action.

Phraseologism is a stable phrase that functions as a separate word, the meaning of which cannot be derived from the meanings of its constituent components. In a broad sense, the term "phraseologism" is applied to any objects, phenomena, actions.

Phraseologism has always been a very popular phenomenon in both written and oral speech. It is used in speech to give a statement expressiveness, emotionality, an assessment of a particular phenomenon, event or object, thereby influencing the reader or listener. In studying the phraseological unit in the theoretical chapter of our final qualification work, we analyzed the main stages of the development of phraseology as a linguistic discipline, the main approaches to the subject and essence of phraseology, the definition of a phraseological unit and its properties, and also conducted comparative analyses of phraseological units with a component - a zoonym in English and Russian, analyzed the syntactic constructions and lexemes used in the paremiology of these languages and, in the end, focused on the expressive means that contribute to the revival of phraseological units and paremias. Having summarized the

various definitions of a phraseological unit, we consider a phraseological unit as an expressive means of language, which is a stable, "winged" expression, consisting in the transfer of the meaning of one object (or class of objects) to another object (or class of objects) based on the similarity of some feature. 43

During the study, the dependence of the phraseology of a certain ethnic group on its worldview, on how a particular nation views the world, life, and reality was established. The attitude of two different nations to the same object could either completely coincide or differ strikingly. This is explained by the fact that different nations, over time, in the course of history, have developed their own character, their own values, each nation has its own geography, flora, and fauna, and, accordingly, each nation is surrounded by its own, unique set of factors that have influenced the phraseology of a particular language.

The work presents a comparative analysis of the proverbs of the English and Russian languages, on the basis of which it can be concluded that the main similarity between them is expressed in the fundamental values, both from a moral and practical point of view. Differences are observed in the way of expressing and distributing norms, the degree of their significance for these cultures. Based on the analysis of the syntactic constructions of proverbs containing a zoonym component in their structure, we came to the conclusion that in linguistics there are only 5 methods of syntactic connection with which paremiological connections are built. These are PP, SO, SPP, SSP and phrases. Also, in the course of the study, we conducted a structural analysis of the syntactic construction of phraseological units, during which it was revealed that there are four structural-semantic types of proverbs in linguistics: Narrative sentences, interrogative sentences, exclamatory sentences and, finally, imperative sentences. It was also established that in the semantics of proverbs, narrative sentences prevail (98 out of 147 studied; 66.5%). The obtained results and conclusions can be used in further linguistic research, in the educational process when considering issues related to the study of phraseology, using phraseological units with a component - a zoonym in the Russian and English languages

References:

1. Akhmanova, O.S. Dictionary of linguistic terms - M.: KomKniga, 2007. - 576 p.
2. Bulygina, T.V. Hidden categories - Linguistic encyclopedic dictionary - V.: ELS, 1990. - 341 p.
3. Linguistic encyclopedic dictionary / ed. V. N. Yartseva. - M.: Soviet Encyclopædia, 1990. - 682 p.